

Year 1

Year 2

Year 3

Year 4

Year 5

List of innovative SLMs and their impact on EPAH established

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Contents

1. Introduction	4
2. List of innovative management practices proposed to reduce the use of pesticides	5
3. EPAH health effect	11
4. References	14

Table of content

Table 1. List of Innovative agricultural management practices proposed to reduce the use of pesticides.	5
Table 2. Hazard of the active ingredients of herbicides, 52 substances considered in the PPDB excluding the metabolites	12
Table 3. Hazard of the active ingredients of insecticides, 46 substances considered in the PPDB excluding the metabolites	12
Table 4. Hazard of the active ingredients of fungicides, 60 substances considered in the PPDB excluding the metabolites	13

1. Introduction

This milestone is entitled "List of innovative SLMs and their impact on EPAH established" and is part of the task 2.5 (Identifying innovative and sustainable land management practices to reduce reliance on PPPs).

The main aim of task 2.5 is to identify ecological alternatives for sustainable plant protection to reduce the reliance on pesticides including low-pesticide-input farming, or other management practices needed for farmers to implement Integrated Pest Management (IPM) and considering the Sustainable Use Directive (SUD). In this task, the selection of innovative techniques for the sustainable land management (SLM) is based on the knowledge gained from the workshops with CSS and national stakeholders (e.g., farm advisors, or technical authorities), and on data available from past and ongoing projects (covered in this milestone).

More specifically, the main aim of this milestone (MS2) is to list the innovative SLM practices that have been shown to help reduce the use of PPPs while reducing the adverse effect of pesticides on health. This milestone will serve as basic material for D2.5 planned for Month 46.

The compilation of the list of SLMs provided in this report was facilitated by our long experience in the field and our knowledge of SLMs available in databases such as WOCAT (<https://www.wocat.net/en/>) and the iSQAPER project (<https://isqaper-is.eu/>). The global SLM Database WOCAT, launched in 1992, contains over 1500 SLM practices from all over the world. In the iSQAPER database, more than 100 SLM based on WOCAT technologies and other sources allowed us to select the most promising SLM that suit our purpose and the European context. We also considered relevant sources such as: Global Soil Partnership (<http://www.fao.org/global-soil-partnership/en/>), and Status of Worlds Soil Resources 2015 available (<http://www.fao.org/3/a-i5199e.pdf>); and projects such as: (e.g., Diverfarming "<http://www.diverfarming.eu/index.php/en/repository-2/practice-abstracts>", DeverIMPACTS <https://www.diverimpacts.net/>, and SoilCare "<https://www.soilcare-project.eu/>").

In addition, we did a targeted literature search to complete and check whether the selected practices reduce or eventually eliminate the harmful effect of excessive pesticide use on health.

The first literature search showed that the adoption of SLMs did reduce or eliminate the use of pesticides. A positive effect on health has not been demonstrated as this fact requires an in-depth study allowing a direct comparison between two different populations: one in contact with pesticides for different uses and the other kept away from such practices. Investigating this issue will require consultation of sensitive databases and is planned as a second step in the framework of the final report D2.5.

2. List of innovative management practices proposed to reduce the use of pesticides

In the Table 1 below, we list the innovative sustainable land management (SLMs) practices to reduce the reliance on pesticides. Most SLMs result from different database, projects, and literature dealing with the same topic (see the references given in Table 1).

Given the lack of literature proving the direct link between the adoption of SLMs and their positive health effect, we highlighted the likely effect of active substances on health in the absence of any sustainable measures. In this case, the adverse effect of active substances was based on the evidence level (human) and the hazard class (ecosystem) provided in the PPDB database (refer to "General information" of Table 1).

We have tried to provide the type of pesticides that would be reduced or eliminated if SLM were adopted in column 4 of Table 1. However, when "pesticides" is reported, it means that it is not known whether they are insecticides, herbicides, or fungicides.

Table 1. List of Innovative agricultural management practices proposed to reduce the use of pesticides.

A broad class of management	Category	Description	General information (for EPAH health effect, see Table 2)
Vegetation management	Vegetation cover	A permanent cover of spontaneous or sown perennial grasses is established between rows in orchards to prevent water erosion and limit the leaching of nutrients (particularly nitrates) and pesticides. <i>Phatak, S.C., Diaz-Perez, J.C. 2012</i> <i>iSQAPER project</i>	No data
	Vegetation bands	Strip cropping to control pests: a type of intercropping that involves planting crops in distinct rows that can be separately managed. <i>Strip cropping - New ways to control pests and diseases in organic farming, FiBL, Project⁽¹⁾; Giaccio et al. (2016); Pavlidis et al., 2020; https://organic.rijkzwaan.com/</i>	Reduction of Glyphosate use (Table 2-4); Aphids are harmless to corn, for example. Those aphids attract spiders, beetles and parasitoid wasps, which then form a 'standing army' for the adjacent strip of cabbages, for example, which are susceptible to damage from aphids."
		Flower strip: encourage natural antagonists of agricultural pests. This helps to reduce pest infestation and hence damage to agricultural crops, as well as avoiding the use of PPP. <i>Tschumi, M. Flower Strips Reduce Pests – Agroscope, Project⁽²⁾</i>	Reduction of pesticides use (Table 2-4)
Crop choice		Intercropping: a practice involving multiple crop species cultivated simultaneously in a single field as an alternative to conventional monoculture cropping Maize and soybean, Soybean helps to fix nitrogen in the soil, reducing the net demand for fertilizers	Four to 5 times more earthworms biomass under maize and beans intercrop compared to maize monocrop, <i>H2020, Diverfarming project</i> More OM in soil. <i>Virginia et al. (2018)</i>

<p>Vegetable lettuce, pak choi, escarole, choy sum and morning glory are intercropped to reduce damage from insects <i>Chai, Q. et al. 2021</i> <i>iSQAPER project</i> <i>TOPPS Project http://www.topps-life.org/</i></p>	
<p>Cover crop mixtures as dead mulch. Cover crops mixture are terminated as a dead mulch for no-till establishment of vegetables, soyabean, grain maize</p> <p>Cover crop as relay intercropping in wheat-based systems Legume cover crops are established by undersowing in winter wheat and grown until following year</p> <p>Coverage crops (bridge crops) that develop between two main rotation crops. They are intended to keep the soil covered to reduce soil degradation processes or for main crops (soil erosion, weed growth, etc.). The biomass generated is used to feed the cattle or can be "drying" to sow the following rotation crop. (In this last case " Dry the cultivation coverage to sow the main culture" one must be cautious because it usually gets with PPP.</p> <p style="text-align: right;"><i>IWMPRAISE</i></p>	<p>Using mechanical form to cut the cultivating coverage to avoid the use of pesticides (Table 2-4)</p>
<p>Allelopathetic cover crops Use of cover crops species that release biochemicals in the soil which are toxic for weed seeds and plantlets, thus contributing to reduce weed establishment at early crop stages</p> <p style="text-align: right;"><i>IWMPRAISE</i></p>	<p>Reduction of herbicides</p>
<p>Cover cropping in vineyards for weed control:</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Inspirational ideas: <i>Weed control in organic viticulture (2020)</i></p>	<p>Reduction of herbicides</p>
<p>Crop rotation/diversification: diversity of plants and associated biota such as arthropod herbivores, predators, and parasites, both above- and below-ground. <i>van der Werf, W., Bianchi, F. 2022</i> <i>IWMPRAISE</i></p>	<p>1. Earthworms abundance and diversity was 90% and 80% higher respectively after 20 y organic potatoes management with rotation and diversification compared to conventional management</p> <p>2. Soil organic matter was 50% higher under organic potatoes farm with rotations and diversification compared to conventional farm, <i>H2020, Diverfarming project</i></p>
<p>Landscape diversification: the spatial arrangement and size influence pest control (configurational heterogeneity) <i>Fahrig et al., 2011; Martin et al. 2019</i></p>	<p>Reduction of pesticides (Table 2-4)</p>
<p>Leguminous crops in plots temporarily set outside the crop rotation for 4-5 years to recover soil fertility and reduce the need for biocides while providing supplemental income.</p> <p>Irrigation: <i>Optimize scheduling - modern precision practices to meet crop water needs (real time needs vs. calendar estimation); amend pesticide use if there are issues (design integrated practices for product application / irrigation)</i></p>	

TOPPS Project <http://www.topps-life.org/>

Carbon and nutrient management	Mulching	<p>Vitiforestry: Vitiforestry refers to agroforestry applied to viticulture. It associates trees and crops on the same plot.</p>	<p>1. The Vitiforest project has shown that the introduction of trees does not have a strong and homogeneous effect on the distribution of pests (green leafhoppers) and arthropods. However, it has an impact on the abundance of earthworms, due to the presence of grass, and on the abundance of certain microbial taxa.</p> <p><i>Vitiforest project, 2021</i></p>
		<p>Straw Mulching: straw mulching is the practice of spreading a layer of straw on the soil surface. It helps conserve moisture, improve fertility and health of the soil and reduce weed growth.</p> <p><i>iSQAPER project</i></p>	<p>The potato harvesting process is simplified and consists only of lifting the potatoes from the surface by harvesters. This technology provides the best temperature regime for the formation of a potato crop, minimizes the machinery impact on the soil and the <u>use of pesticides</u> (Table 2-4)</p> <p><i>Pastukhov et al., 2020</i></p>
		<p>Biodegradable plastic mulches: Mulching improves crop yield, decreases pesticide inputs to the field, saves irrigation water, and have emerged as a promising alternative to alleviate polyethylene pollution.</p> <p><i>Serrano-Ruiz et al., 2021</i></p>	
Mechanical weed control	Robotic weeders	<p>Robotic weeders: Commercially available camera-guided cultivators have two major components: machine detection of the crop, and actuators that control the weeds; there are four primary physical weed control actuators that may be coupled with a weed detection system: (i) mechanical intra- and inter-row cultivation, (ii) thermal weed control, (iii) abrasion, and (iv) mowing.</p> <p><i>Fennimore, S., and Cutulle, M. 2018; Melander et al., 2015 ; Kaierle et al., 2013 ; Knezevic et al., 2016 ; Wortman, 2015; Cloutier et al., 2007 ; SoilCare project</i></p>	<p><u>Reduction of herbicides (Table 2)</u></p>
Weed management	Bioherbicides	<p>Bioherbicides are derived either from plants containing phytotoxic allelochemicals or certain disease-carrying microbes that can suppress weed populations.</p> <p><i>Hasan et al., 2021; Radhakrishnan et al., 2012</i></p>	<p><u>Reduction in herbicides (Table 2)</u></p>
	Weed genomics	<p>Sustained advances in genome sequencing and assembly technologies make it possible for individual research groups to generate reference genomes for multiple weed species at reasonable costs</p> <p><i>Ravet et al., 2018; Martin et al., 2019; Montarry et al., 2021</i></p>	<p><u>Reduction of herbicides (Table 2)</u></p>
	Plant hormones	<p>Plant hormones such as gibberellic acid (GA3) and abscisic acid (ABA) have the potential to induce seed germination and seed dormancy, respectively reducing selection pressure and weed infestations until crop canopy closure. Prior to crop emergence, plant hormones are tank mixed with PRE herbicides and sprayed to cover crop residue.</p> <p><i>Oliveira et al., 2020</i></p>	<p><u>Reduction of herbicides (Table 2)</u></p>

Pest management	Plant-based natural products	<p>Natural plant products with bioactivity toward insects include several classes of molecules, e.g. terpenes, flavonoids, alkaloids, polyphenols, cyanogenic glucosides, quinones, amides, aldehydes, thiophenes, amino acids, saccharides and polyketides (which is not an exhaustive list of insecticidal substances)</p> <p><i>Souto et al., 2021 ; Tlak Gajger et al., 2021 ; Essential oils – Fierascu et al (2019)</i></p>	<u>Reduction of insecticides (Table 3)</u>
	Algal metabolites	<p>The term algae encompasses a wide range of photosynthetic organisms that are found primarily in freshwater and marine environments. They have proven to be effective antibacterial, antiviral, antifungal, nematocides, insecticides, herbicides, and plant growth stimulants.</p> <p><i>Asimakis et al., 2022</i></p>	Reduction of pesticides (Table 2-4)
	Basic substances	<p>Are approved for use in the EU and are products that are already sold for certain purposes, e.g. as a foodstuff or a cosmetic, but which can also serve as plant protection products. They are used to manage postharvest diseases of fresh fruit, vegetables and aromatic plants and to the management of seedborne pathogens on several crops (cereals, vegetables, etc.), for which there is a reduced number of effective synthetic pesticides.</p> <p><i>Euphresco. BasicS Project. 2021⁽³⁾; Romanazzi et al., 2022</i></p>	<u>Reduction of insecticides (Table 2)</u>
	Microbial inoculants	<p>These are beneficial microorganisms that seem to have every potential to provide an alternative opportunity to overcome the ill effects of various components of traditional agriculture being practiced by and large.</p> <p><i>Gupta et al., 2022; Microbe-induced resistance for enhancing plant resistance to insect pests: MIRA project: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/765290</i></p>	<u>Reduction of insecticides (Table 2)</u>
	Biosolarization	<p>Instead of toxic conventional pesticides, biosolarization uses solar heating and microbial activity to create soil conditions that are lethal to many pests, but safe for humans. Spread a biodegradable organic matter amendment on the soil (e.g. rice bran, mustard meal, or certain food processing residues such as almond hulls and shells or tomato skins and seeds). Usually, around 9 tons per acre will suffice. Incorporate it into the soil down to 6-12 inches.</p> <p><i>UCDAVIS-Western Center for Agricultural Health and Safety, 2020</i></p>	<u>Reduction of insecticides (Table 2)</u>
	UV-C	<p>UV-C flashes are being tested in the fight against powdery mildew, to reduce the use of fungicides. The UV-C flashes cause abiotic stress in the vine which reacts by an accumulation of defense compounds. Thus, the vine is better able to <u>fight against pathogens</u>.</p> <p><i>https://ecophytopic.fr/sites/default/files/2021-10/Fiche%20Pratique%20-%20UV-C.pdf</i></p>	<u>Reduction of fungicides (Table 3)</u>
Disease management	Plant-growth promoting	<p>These are naturally occurring beneficial microbial bio-control agents considered as an environmentally sound option to manage</p>	Reduction of pesticides (Table 2-4)

bacteria (PGPB)	diseases; biocontrol agents such as <i>Hypericumgramineum</i> , <i>Bacillus</i> spp., <i>Pseudomonas fluorescens</i> , some species of <i>Streptomyces</i> , <i>Ulocladium</i> spp. and <i>Trichoderma</i> spp. are considered as promising biocontrol agents against phytopathogens.	
		<i>Abbas et al., 2019</i>
Biofungicides	Biofungicides (based on <i>Trichoderma viride</i>) are used for seed and soil treatment to suppress various diseases caused by fungal pathogens (e.g. <i>Rhizoctonia</i> , <i>Pythium</i> , <i>Armillaria</i>).	<u>Reduction of fungicides (Table 3)</u>
		<i>Ehiobu et al., 2022; iSQAPER</i>
	RNAi-Based Biofungicides that use double-stranded RNA (dsRNA) to target essential fungal genes are considered an emerging approach for controlling devastating gray mold diseases.	<u>Reduction of fungicides (Table 3)</u>
		<i>Islam and Sherif, 2020</i>
Choosing disease-resistant varieties	Disease-resistant plants are chosen to eliminate the need for additional efforts to reduce losses caused by a specific disease. Resistant plants are developed using standard breeding procedures (selection and/or hybridization) or through genetic engineering.	Reduction of pesticides (Table 2-4)
	<i>iSQAPER; Huang et al., 2022</i>	
	Reduction of disease symptoms on the vines. (<i>Resdur project</i>) https://www.vinopole.com/recherches-experimentations-vitivinicoles/materiel-vegetal/varietes-resistantes/varietes-resistantes/	
Antibiotic suppression	Antibiotics are applied to the crop by spray, with ground equipment or added into an irrigation system. They are microbial toxins, some of which have been shown to be particularly effective at suppressing plant pathogens and the diseases they cause (e.g. <i>Bacillus Amyloliquefaciens</i> , <i>Pseudomonas fluorescens</i>).	Reduction of pesticides (Table 2-4)
		<i>iSQAPER ; Jayaraman et al., 2021 ; Thomashow et al., 2019</i>
Grafting	Plants with a higher resistance to pest and diseases are produced by grafting seedlings onto resistant root stocks of other plants (e.g. courgette onto wild eggplant).	Reduction of pesticides (Table 2-4)
		<i>Karaca et al., 2020; iSQAPER</i>
Pesticide plant extracts	These are unrefined plant extracts for pest control having several advantages in terms of preventing the development of insecticide resistance due to the usual presence of several bio-active compounds, their low persistence in the environment, and their generally low cost of use (e.g. <i>T. vogelii</i> , <i>T. diversifolia</i> , and <i>L. javanica</i>)	Reduction of pesticides (Table 2-4)
		<i>Tembo et al., 2018</i>
Biological control	Biological control is a method of plant disease management by inhibiting plant pathogens, improving plant immunity, and/or modifying the environment through the effects of beneficial microorganisms, compounds, or healthy cropping systems (e.g. <i>Trichoderma harzianum</i> Rifai, <i>Pochonia</i>	Reduction of pesticides (Table 2-4)

	<p>chlamydosporia (Goddard) Zare and Gams, and Paecilomyces lilacinus (Thom) Samson)</p> <p><i>He et al., 2021 ; Wei et al., 2015 ; Bonaterra et al., 2022 ; Rega et al 2018 – modelled and assessed landscape potential to sustain natural pest control.</i></p> <p>Biopesticides: <i>Innovative bio-based pesticides to minimise chemical residue risk on food:</i> https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/324416</p>	
Microbial inoculants	<p>Microbial inoculants such as Endophytes and rhizobacteria are known to have plant growth-promoting, nutrient-fortifying, and biotic and abiotic stress-alleviating potential for different crop plants and have greater potential to be used as microbial inoculants; they are reported to protect plants from various biotic and abiotic stresses along with biofertilization and biofortification in crops of nutritional importance.</p> <p><i>Gupta et al., 2022; Malviya et al., 2020 ; Singh et al., 2021 ; Yadav et al., 2022</i></p>	Reduction of pesticides (Table 2-4)
Integrated pest and disease management	<p>Integrated pest and disease management is a broad-based approach that considers all available pest and disease control techniques and integrates appropriate measures. The aim is to discourage the development of pest populations and diseases, keeping interventions to levels that are economically justified, and reducing or minimizing risks to the environment, soil and aquatic life and human health.</p> <p><i>iSQAPER; OPTIMA project⁽⁴⁾; Integrated pest management and sustainable agriculture, project⁽⁵⁾</i></p>	Reduction of pesticides (Table 2-4)
Pest and disease monitoring	<p>Several tools are available for pest and disease monitoring including apps for disease recognition and sticky traps for insect monitoring. Monitoring is the basis for integrated pest and disease management.</p> <p><i>Rustia et al., 2022; iSQAPER; FF-IPM project - https://platform.fruitflies-ipm.eu/product-category/tools/ TOPPS Project http://www.topps-life.org/</i></p> <p>Risk assessment of disease levels: Eyespot for assessing eyespot risk in wheat (informs whether there is a need for pesticides) https://ahdb.org.uk/knowledge-library/eyespot-in-cereals-and-risk-assessment-in-wheat</p>	Reduction of pesticides (Table 2-4)
	<p>A system called Intelligent and Integrated Pest and Disease Management (I2 PDM) system was developed. Edge computing devices were developed to automatically detect and recognize major greenhouse insect pests such as thrips (Frankliniella intonsa, Thrips hawaiiensis, and Thrips tabaci), and whiteflies (Bemisia argentifolii and Trialeurodes vaporariorum).</p> <p><i>Rustia et al., 2022</i></p>	Reduction of insecticides (Table 2)
	<p>Integrated acquisition of geospatial and referenced data used to increase the understanding of intra- and inter-farm variability of crop pest and disease observations and management for decision-support system analytics.</p> <p><i>Tonnang et al., 2022</i></p>	Reduction of pesticides (Table 2-4)
	<p>Noninvasive Early Disease Diagnosis: sensors, biosensors, and clinical instruments developed for the noninvasive early detection</p>	Reduction of pesticides (Table 2-4)

		and diagnosis of human, animal, and plant diseases or invasive pests. <i>Wilson, 2020</i>	
	Pheromone dispensers	Pheromone dispensers are used to disrupt the mating of certain insects (e.g. moths in vineyards) in order to increase yield while at the same time preserving biodiversity and the sensitive balance of the ecosystem. Pheromone use diminishes the need for insecticides. <i>Desauziers et al., 2022; Gavara et al., 2020; Klassen et al., 2023; iSQAPER</i>	<u>Reduction of insecticides (Table 2)</u>
	Winter food fields	Winter food fields are not harvested and ploughed until the following spring. They serve as an important food source of grains and herbs and provide refuge for wintering field birds and mice. A more complete food web develops, ensuring lower sensitivity to pests and diseases. <i>iSQAPER; Heroldová et al., 2021</i>	Reduction of pesticides (Table 2-4)
	Tree buffer zones	Indigenous trees are used to create a buffer zone between fields, preventing the spread of diseases. The trees also enhance the biodiversity of the area. <i>iSQAPER; Pavlidis et al., 2018; Passeport et al., 2014</i>	Reduction of pesticides (Table 2-4)
	Optimal timing of pesticide applications	The timing of herbicide and pesticide applications is optimized to reduce the amount applied. Multiple factors (including the time of day, season, stage of crop growth and local weather conditions) should be taken into account in order to make most efficient use of the products and reduce unnecessary pollution. <i>Griffin and Zapata, 2016; Gao et al., 2020; iSQAPER</i>	Possible reduction of pesticides and <u>herbicides</u> (Table 2-4)
Farm equipment	Weed control	Electric weeding: Weeds will be destroyed by the passage of the electric arc (2. ongoing research on the impact of earthworm populations, bacteria, fungi.) https://qeco.ecophytopic.fr/qeco/Concept/Desherbage_Electrique_En_Vigne	<u>Reduce of herbicides (Table 2)</u>

3. EPAH health effect

As the positive effect of agricultural practices is not explicitly reported in the literature, we highlighted the likely hazard of the active substances on health in the absence of any sustainable measures (see chapter 2). This was based on the evidence level (human) and the hazard class (ecosystem) provided in the PPDB database. We considered the 209 active substances considered in SPRINT, among which we selected the ones (excluding metabolites) that are documented in PPDB.

We have listed the hazard of each substance by category (insecticides, herbicides, and fungicides) and counted the number of substances of responsible for that particular hazard and its corresponding percentage with regard to the total substances considered. We have numbered only the substances that have a high hazard class and high evidence level on the health of different ecosystems and human compartments, respectively, if no action is taken to reduce the pesticides through SLMs. Table 2 provides hazard of the active ingredients of herbicides.

Table 2. Hazard of the active ingredients of herbicides, 52 substances considered in the PPDB excluding the metabolites

Order	Hazard	Number of substances responsible of the hazard	Percentage of substances responsible of the hazard
1	Mammals - Short term dietary NOEL mg/kg	40	76.92
2	Human - Eye irritant	15	28.85
	Human - Respiratory tract irritant	15	28.85
3	Aquatic plants - Acute 7d EC50 mg/l	16	30.77
4	Human - Reproduction development effects	14	26.92
5	Human - Skin irritant	9	17.31
	Human - Skin sensitiser	9	17.31
6	Human - Carcinogen	6	11.54
7	Human - Endocrine disrupter	4	7.69
	Human - Neurotoxicant	4	7.69
8	Algae - Acute 72hr EC50 growth mg/l	3	5.77
	Algae - Chronic 96hr NOEC mg/l	3	5.77
9	Honeybees - Contact acute 48hr LD50 ug/bee	2	3.85
	Fish - Chronic 21d NOEC mg/l	2	3.85

In the case of insecticides, we reported a total of 46 from the PPBP database excluding metabolites. We have numbered only the substances that have a high hazard class and high evidence level on the health of different ecosystems and human compartments, respectively, if no action is taken to reduce the pesticides through SLMs (Table 3).

Table 3. Hazard of the active ingredients of insecticides, 46 substances considered in the PPDB excluding the metabolites

Order	Hazard	Number of substances responsible of the hazard	Percentage of substances responsible of the hazard
1	Mammals - Short term dietary NOEL mg/kg	33	71.74
2	Honeybeesbee - Contact acute 48hr LD50 ug/bee	25	54.35
3	Honeybees - Oral acute 48hr LD50 ug	22	47.83
4	Aquatic invertebrates - Acute 48hr EC50 mg/l	21	45.65
	Aquatic invertebrates - Chronic 21d NOEC mg/l	18	39.13
5	Human - Neurotoxicant	18	39.13
	Sediment - dwelling organisms Acute 96hr LC50	18	39.13
6	Sediment - dwelling organisms: Chronic 28d NOEC static water	17	36.96
7	Aquatic crustaceans - Acute 96hr LC50 mg/l	15	32.61
	Fish - Acute 96hr LC50 mg/l	14	30.43
8	Human - Skin irritant	14	30.43
	Human - Eye irritant	14	30.43
9	Fish - Chronic 21d NOEC mg/l	13	28.26
10	Sediment dwelling organisms - Chronic 28d NOEC sediment	12	26.09
	Human - Reproduction development effects	12	26.09
11	Human - Skin sensitiser	10	21.74
	Mammals - Acute oral LD50 mg/kg BW/day	10	21.74
	Birds - Acute LD50 mg/kg	10	21.74

12	Human - Endocrine disrupter	8	17.39
	Human - Acetyl cholinesterase inhibitor.	8	17.39
	Human - Respiratory tract irritant	8	17.39
13	Human - Carcinogen	5	10.87
14	Earthworms - Acute 14d LC50 mg/kg	4	8.70
	Algae - Acute 72hr EC50 growth mg/l	4	8.70
15	Honeybees - Unknown mode acute 48hr LD50 ug/bee.	3	6.52
16	Algae - Chronic 96hr NOEC mg/l	2	4.35
17	Birds - Short term dietary LC50 LD51	1	2.17
	Aquatic plants - Acute 7d EC50 mg/l	1	2.17

In the case of fungicides, we reported a total of 60 active substance from the PPBP database excluding metabolites. We have numbered only the substances that have a high hazard class and high evidence level on the health of different ecosystems and human compartments, respectively, if no action is taken to reduce the pesticides through SLMs (Table 4).

Table 4. Hazard of the active ingredients of fungicides, 60 substances considered in the PPDB excluding the metabolites

Order	Hazard	Number of substances responsible of the hazard	Percentage of substances responsible of the hazard
1	Mammals - Short term dietary NOEL mg/kg	51	85.00
2	Human - Eye irritant	23	38.33
3	Human - Reproduction development effects	16	26.67
4	Human - Respiratory tract irritant	14	23.33
5	Aquatic invertebrates - Chronic 21d NOEC mg/l	11	18.33
	Human - Skin sensitiser	10	16.67
6	Fish - Acute 96hr LC50 mg/l	10	16.67
	Fish - Chronic 21d NOEC mg/l	10	16.67
7	Aquatic invertebrates - Acute 48hr EC50 mg/l	7	11.67
8	Aquatic crustaceans - Acute 96hr LC50 mg/l	6	10.00
9	Algae - Acute 72hr EC50 growth mg/l	5	8.33
	Sediment - dwelling organisms: Chronic 28d NOEC static water	3	5.00
10	Human - Carcinogen	3	5.00
	Earthworms - Chronic 14d NOEC reproduction mg/kg	2	3.33
	Sediment - dwelling organisms Acute 96hr LC50	2	3.33
	Sediment dwelling organisms - Chronic 28d NOEC sediment	2	3.33
11	Aquatic plants - Acute 7d EC50 mg/l	2	3.33
	Human - Mutagen	2	3.33
	Human - Endocrine disrupter	2	3.33
	Human - Neurotoxicant	2	3.33
	Mammals - Acute oral LD50 mg/kg BW/day	1	1.67
12	Birds - Acute LD50 mg/kg	1	1.67
	Birds - Short term dietary LC50 LD51	1	1.67
	Earthworms - Acute 14d LC50 mg/kg	1	1.67
	Algae - Chronic 96hr NOEC mg/l	1	1.67

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